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НЕКОТОРЫЕ ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ БЛОКАД ПРИ АБДОМИНАЛЬНОМ РОДОРАЗРЕШЕНИИ ЖЕНЩИН С УМЕРЕННО ВЫРАЖЕННЫМ МИТРАЛЬНЫМ СТЕНОЗОМ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Исследование проводилось с целью определения наиболее рационального и безопасного варианта регионарной анестезии при абдоминальном родоразрешении у больных с «умеренно выраженным» митральным стенозом площадью 2,9-2,0см² и сниженными коронарными резервами. В последние были включены 51 женщины. В зависимости от варианта анестезии все пациентки разделены на три равные группы. У пациенток I-й группы проводилась в условиях спинальной анестезии, II-й - в условиях эпидуральной анестезии, пациентки III-й группы оперированы в условиях сбалансированной эпидуральной анестезии сниженными концентрациями местного анестетика в сочетании с фентанилом и превентивной анальгезией. На этапах анестезии и операции изучена центральная и периферическая гемодинамика функциональное состояние симпатoadrenalовой и гипоталамо-гипофизарной систем. Установлено что наиболее рациональным и безопасным способом обезболивания у пациентов с митральным стенозом и сниженными коронарными резервами является эпидуральная анестезия со сниженными концентрациями бупивакаина гидрохлорида в сочетании с фентанилом и превентивной анальгезией.

Ключевые слова: спинальная анестезия, варианты эпидуральной анестезии, кесарево сечение, митральный стеноз, коронарные резервы.

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О'RTACHA IFODALANGAN MITRAL STENOZLI AYOLLARDA KESARCHA-KESISH AMALIYOTI DAVRIDA MARKAZIY BLOKLARNI QO'LLASH SAMARADORLIGINING BA'ZI KO'RSATKICHLARI

АННОТАЦИЯ

Tadqiqot maydoni 2, 9-2, 0 sm² bo'lgan "o'rtacha ifodalangan" mitral stenozi va koronar zaxiralari pasaygan homiladorlarda kesarcha-kesish jarayonida mahalliy og'riqsizlantirish eng oqilona va xavfsiz variantni aniqlash uchun o'tkazildi. 51-nafar ayol tatqiqotdan o'tkazildi. Anesteziya turiga qarab, barcha bemorlar uchta teng guruhga bo'lingan. I guruh bemorlarida operatsiya spinal anesteziya ostida, II guruhda, epidural anesteziya ostida, III guruhdagi bemorlarda kesarcha-kesish jarayonida og'riqsizlantirish kontsentratsiyasi pasaytirilgan muvozanatlashtirilgan mahalliy anestetik bilan fentanilning birgalikda qo'llanishi o'tkazildi. Anesteziya va jarrohlik bosqichlarida simpatoadrenal va gipotalamo-gipofizar tizimlarning markaziy va periferik gemodinamikasi va funktsional holati o'rganildi. Aniqlanishicha, mitral stenozi va koronar zaxiralari kamaygan

bemorlarda og'riqni yo'qotishning eng oqilona va xavfsiz usuli bupivakain gidroxlordning fentanil bilan birgalikda pasaytirilgan kontsentratsiyasi bilan epidural anesteziya hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlari: spinal anesteziya, epidural anesteziya variantlari, kesar kesish, mitral stenoz, koronar zaxira

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SOME INDICATORS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CENTRAL BLOCKS IN ABDOMINAL DELIVERY OF WOMEN WITH MODERATE MITRAL STENOSIS

ANNOTATION

This study was conducted to determine the most rational and safe option for regional anaesthesia during abdominal delivery in patients with "moderately expressed" mitral stenosis with an area of 2.9-2.0 cm² and reduced coronary reserves. The study included 51 women with these conditions. Depending on the anaesthesia option, all patients were divided into three equal groups. Patients in the first group underwent spinal anaesthesia, those in the second group underwent epidural anaesthesia, and patients in the third group were operated on under balanced epidural anaesthesia with reduced concentrations of local anaesthetic in combination with fentanyl and preventive analgesia. Central and peripheral hemodynamics and the functional state of the sympathoadrenal and hypothalamohypophyseal systems were studied during the stages of anaesthesia and surgery. The most rational and safe method of analgesia in patients with MS and reduced coronary reserves is epidural anaesthesia with reduced concentrations of bupivacaine hydrochloride in combination with fentanyl and preventive analgesia.

Keywords: spinal anaesthesia, options for epidural anaesthesia, caesarean section, mitral stenosis, coronary reserves.

The choice of an anaesthetic approach for cesarean section in patients with mitral stenosis (MS) was made based on the degree of stenosis and the functional state of the cardiovascular system at the time of childbirth within the timeframes recommended by the Association of Obstetricians of the Republic Scientific Center for Maternal and Child Health and the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The most rational method of anaesthetic support for cesarean section is considered to be central (neuroaxial) blocks (CNBs), particularly spinal anaesthesia (SA). However, their use in patients with reduced coronary reserves due to mitral stenosis may be accompanied by significant hemodynamic disturbances caused by a high segmental block and a decrease in the adaptive capacity of the cardiovascular system (ACVS). This is particularly challenging in patients with moderately expressed mitral stenosis in an area of 2.9-2.0 cm², where inadequate circulation and a hypokinetic circulation mode develop as early as 34-36 weeks of gestation. Pregnant women with mitral stenosis in this range are considered high-risk patients for intra- and postpartum (postoperative) complications and require an individualized approach in each specific clinical situation. Therefore, studying the hemodynamic status of pregnant women with mitral stenosis during the use of CNB is particularly important for determining the safest and most acceptable anaesthesia methodology in obstetric practice.

Research Objective: To evaluate circulatory parameters; respiratory function; and indicators of the autonomic, sympathoadrenal, and hypothalamohypophyseal-adrenocortical systems during anaesthesia and surgery in pregnant women with moderately expressed mitral stenosis (MS) and reduced adaptational capacities of the cardiovascular system. To assess the effectiveness of spinal anaesthesia (SA) and options for epidural anaesthesia (EA) during cesarean section.

Materials and Methods: This study is based on the results of clinical observations and a complex of clinical-functional and biochemical studies during cesarean section (CS) in 51 women aged >20-28 years at a gestational age of 34-36 weeks. All patients had moderate mitral stenosis (A. N. Okorokov). The indication for preterm delivery in this group of patients was progressing circulatory insufficiency associated with increasing gestational age, according to multifactorial criteria for the degree of preservation of coronary reserves (reference to your articles, Samarkand, with your names, 7). According to all 51 observations, the adaptive capacities of the cardiovascular system were reduced. The operations were performed as planned, with a duration of 30-60 minutes. The patients were divided into 3 equal

groups according to the method of anaesthesia. Patients in Group I (n=37) underwent surgery under spinal anaesthesia (SA), and Group II (n=37) underwent surgery under traditional epidural anaesthesia (EA). In 27 patients in Group III, EA was performed with reduced concentrations of local anaesthetic in combination with fentanyl.

The anaesthesia procedure was as follows: after intravenous administration of diphenhydramine (dimedrol) at a dose of 0.2 mg/kg and dexamethasone (0.07 mg/kg). In Group I, the subarachnoid space was punctured at the level of LII-LIV, after which 2.0-2.5 ml (10, 12.5 mg) of 0.5% hyperbaric solution of bupivacaine hydrochloride was introduced. The dose of bupivacaine hydrochloride was calculated according to the individual morphometric characteristics of the patient [8, 7, 5].

In Group II, after similar premedication procedures under local infiltrative anaesthesia in a lateral position at the level of the ThXII-VLI, puncture and catheterization of the epidural space were performed. The catheter was introduced cranially by 4+5 cm, followed by the introduction of a test dose (2.0 ml of 2% lidocaine hydrochloride solution). In the absence of signs of SA, a 0.5% isobaric solution of bupivacaine hydrochloride was slowly introduced fractionally through the epidural catheter, calculated at 1.25-1.5 ml per spinal segment. The EA technique used in Group III differed from the previous technique by using preventive analgesia with paracetamol, which was administered intravenously immediately before puncture and catheterization of the epidural space in the form of a 1% solution in a volume of 100 ml (infulgan) [10, 11, 4], as well as the use of 0.375% bupivacaine hydrochloride solution in combination with fentanyl (1.4 mcg/kg). The operation began with the appearance of clinical signs of complete segmental motor blockade. Patients were placed in the "left uterus" position, and the head and middle segments of the operating table were raised by 10-15° (Fowler's position). After the extraction of the foetus, diazepam (0.2 mg/kg) was administered intravenously to reduce psychoemotional tension.

The effectiveness of analgesia was assessed based on commonly accepted clinical signs. The sensory block was evaluated by the loss of pain sensitivity (pin prick test). The upper limit of the blockade was assessed after stabilization. To assess the depth of motor blockade, the P. Bromage scale was used. Central hemodynamics were studied using echocardiography with an SA-600 device (Medison). The stroke index (SI), cardiac index (CI), total peripheral vascular resistance (TPVR),

mean dynamic pressure (MDP), heart rate (HR), and hemoglobin saturation (SpO2) were monitored using a Schiller monitor (4, 9, 15).

Information on the impact of different CNB options on respiratory function (RR, TV, MV, MVL) and gas exchange (SpO2) in patients with moderately expressed MS is presented in Table 1.

As shown in the table, the preoperative respiratory function and gas exchange indices in Groups 3, 4, and 5 were identical and did not significantly differ from each other. Moderate hyperventilation (26-22.7-23.1 L/min), a decrease in MV (42.9-43.8 L/min), and a decrease in SpO2 (92.8-93.1%) were notable. These indicators significantly differed from those in patients in Groups 1 and 2 and were primarily associated with haemodynamic insufficiency caused by the severity of MS.

Before the skin incision, a significant reduction in the RR of 15.5%, 13%, and 11% was recorded in all three study groups (3, 4, 5). VE tended to decrease. The TV and MV in Group 3 patients significantly decreased by 21.1% and 11.8%, respectively. SpO2 levels remained unchanged (Table 1).

Changes in TV, MV, and MVL in women in Groups 4 and 5 were similar but were not as pronounced (Table 1). The absolute values of MV in Groups 2 and 3 decreased by only 10.7% and 5.9%, respectively, and the MVL decreased by 6.5% and 4.2%, respectively (see absolute values in Table 1).

The above can be explained by the partial blockade of intercostal nerves, which is more pronounced when using SA. The degree of impairment of hemodynamic parameters played a certain role in the development of moderately expressed depression of lung ventilation and respiratory mechanics.

At the most traumatic stages of the operation, the parameters characterizing the effectiveness of spontaneous breathing in all three study groups, relative to the previous stage of the study, did not significantly change. There was a tendency toward an increase in SpO2, which can be explained by periodic oxygen inhalation throughout the entire operation. Notably, the respiratory rate (RR) significantly increased relative to that in the previous stage of the study, approaching the preoperative values (Table 1). No clinical signs of respiratory depression were observed.

The conclusion of the operation was accompanied by a clear trend toward normalization of the studied parameters characterizing the functional state of external respiration and gas exchange (see Table 1) without significant intergroup differences. Attention was given to the increase in VE in all three study groups relative to that in the previous stage of the study (Table 1), which can be explained by the normalization of respiratory function due to childbirth and the consequent restoration of physiological relationships between internal organs and normalization of intra-abdominal pressure.

Twenty-four hours after the operation, there was progressive improvement in the studied parameters characterizing pulmonary ventilation, respiratory mechanics, and gas exchange. The studied indicators significantly exceeded the absolute preoperative values (Table 1).

R in Groups 3, 4, and 5 was 20.6±0.5, 19.8±0.3, and 20.1±0.4 per minute, respectively; VE – 0.62±0.03, 0.63±0.04, and 0.61±0.03 litres; MVV – 48.8±2.0, 48.1±2.1, and 48.4±1.9 L/min. The SpO2 level was 95.1±1.2–95.3±1.3%.

Table 1

Some indicators characterizing the function of external respiration and SpO2 at the stages of anaesthesia and surgery in pregnant women with "moderately expressed" atrioventricular septal stenosis (2.9-2 cm2).

Stages of the research	Groups	The Studied Parameters				
		RR, per minute	TV, ml/kg	MV, l	MVL, л/мин	SpO2, %
On the operating table	1	22,7±0,5	0,54±0,03	12,3±0,4	43,8±1,9	92,8±1,3
	2	23,1±0,4	0,53±0,05	12,2±0,5	42,9±2,5	92,9±1,2
	3	22,9±0,5	0,51±0,03	11,9±0,6	43,2±2,1	93,1±1,4
Before the skin incision	1	19,8±0,3 ©	0,49±0,03	9,7±0,4 ©	38,6±2,1 ©	92,6±1,1
	2	20,1±0,3 ©	0,53±0,03	10,9±0,4 ©	40,1±2,0	92,4±1,4
	3	20,9±0,4 ©	0,54±0,05	11,2±0,6	41,4±2,3	92,5±1,2
Traumatic stage	1	21,8±0,3 Δ	0,49±0,03	10,8±0,5	-	93,2±0,9
	2	22,6±0,4 Δ	0,51±0,03	11,4±0,6	-	93,8±1,1
	3	23,1±0,5 Δ	0,49±0,04	11,3±0,4	-	93,6±1,2
End of the operation	1	20,2±0,4	0,55±0,02 Δ	11,2±0,4	43,9±2,1	94,3±1,3
	2	21,8±0,3	0,59±0,03 Δ	12,6±0,6	43,2±2,3	94,2±1,2
	3	21,3±0,4	0,61±0,04 © Δ	12,8±0,4	42,6±3,1	94,8±1,1
after 24 hours	1	20,6±0,5 ©	0,62±0,03 ©	12,8±0,5	48,8±2,0 © Δ	95,1±1,2
	2	19,8±0,3 ©	0,63±0,04 ©	12,5±0,6	48,1±2,1 © Δ	95,3±1,3
	3	20,1±0,4 ©	0,61±0,03 ©	12,3±0,6	48,4±1,9 © Δ	95,2±1,3

Note: © - significant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to baseline values; Δ - significant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to the previous stage of the study; ● - significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the 3rd and 4th study groups; □ - significant difference compared to the 5th group.

Thus, the tested variants of central nervous block (CNB) do not exert a pronounced depressive effect on the function of external respiration or gas exchange. Moreover, it is necessary to note that when spinal anaesthesia (SA) is used at the level of segmental sensory-motor blockade, moderate depression of respiratory function occurs, which requires correction. The adequacy of anaesthesia was assessed using the tension index (TI), utilizing mathematical analysis of heart rate (9), the level of total cortisol (TC) in the blood plasma (radioimmunoassay method), and the rate of norepinephrine (NE) excretion in the urine (10).

The research was conducted in four stages:

1. On the operating table;
2. Before the skin incision;
3. At the most traumatic stage of the operation (extraction of the foetus, abdominal cavity revision);
4. After the completion of the operation.

All the numerical values obtained during the study were analysed via variational statistics with Student's t test (Microsoft Excel) and are presented in the form of $M \pm m$, where M is the arithmetic mean and m is the standard error of the mean. Differences were considered to be statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. The results obtained are presented in Table 3.

Results and Discussion: Characterizing the clinical course of spinal anaesthesia (SA) in the first group, it should be noted that classical signs of complete segmental sensory-motor block developed by the 6th-8th minute after subarachnoid administration of the calculated dose of local anaesthetic and persisted for 1.5-2 hours. Moreover, the segmental level of the sensory block corresponded to the Th5-Th6 dermatomes. When using variants of epidural anaesthesia (EA) (groups 2-3), signs of a complete segmental sensory-motor block developed by the 15th-18th minute, and the segmental level of the sensory block corresponded to Th7-Th9 dermatomes, with the surgical stage of EA lasting 1.5-2 hours. It should be noted that in patients in the third group, a pronounced sedative effect was observed 8-10 minutes after the epidural administration of analgesic solutions, probably due to the systemic action of fentanyl, which subsequently prevented the administration of benzodiazepines. Throughout the entire operation, including during its most traumatic stages, patients in all three study groups did not react, did not complain, and did not require additional analgesia. No signs of respiratory depression were observed. However, the absolute values of SpO2 did not exceed 94-96%, requiring periodic

oxygen inhalation. The initial hemodynamic status in all three study groups corresponded to a hypodynamic type of circulation. There was marked tachycardia, a significant decrease in one-time and minute cardiac output relative to the expected values, increased mean dynamic pressure, and total peripheral vascular resistance, while minute diuresis corresponded to the lower limits of its physiological fluctuations (see Table 1). No intergroup differences in the studied parameters were detected. Against this background, sufficiently pronounced activation of the sympathetic division of the autonomic nervous system (ANS) was observed. However, this did not exceed the limits of physiological fluctuations (the tension indices ranged from 336.4 ± 20.6 to 349.4 ± 35.7 arbitrary units). The predominance of a negative balance of sympathetic activity is associated with pregnancy, a decrease in coronary reserves, and insufficient circulation, which negatively affects the main life support systems of parturients. The concentrations of total cholesterol (TC) in the blood plasma and total nitrogen (NE) in the urine were also greater in these patients than in patients with a normally progressing pregnancy at 34-36+6 weeks. No significant intergroup differences in the studied parameters were detected.

Before the skin incision, against the background of a full segmental block in patients in all three groups, classical clinical-functional manifestations of central segmental blocks were registered—a decrease in heart rate, a decrease in mean dynamic pressure, and total peripheral vascular resistance (see Table 1)—which were significantly more pronounced when using SA. Thus, in the first group of patients, the mean dynamic pressure and total peripheral vascular resistance decreased by 28.9% and 17.2%, respectively, and the heart rate decreased by 11.4%. This required vasopressor support.

Against this background, the cardiac index (CI) significantly decreased from 2.43 ± 0.04 to 1.97 ± 0.06 l/m²/min. In the same period, in patients in the second group, changes in the studied parameters of hemodynamics were not as pronounced. The mean dynamic pressure and total peripheral vascular resistance decreased by 16.4% and 10.3%, respectively, and the heart rate decreased by 6.4%. The CI tended to decrease, reaching 2.28 ± 0.09 l/m²/min. In patients in the third group, minimal hemodynamic changes occurred. The mean dynamic pressure and total peripheral vascular resistance decreased by only 9.1% and 4.8%, respectively, and the heart rate decreased by 2.7%. The CI was 2.72 ± 0.09 l/m²/min.

Table 2

Some indicators of hemodynamics and peripheral blood circulation at the stages of anaesthesia and surgery in patients with moderately expressed MS (2.9-2 cm²)

Stages of the research	The Studied Parameters					
	Groups	HR per minute	SBP, mmHg	CI, l/min/m ²	TPR, dyn·s/cm ⁻⁵	Minute Diuresis, ml/min
On the operating table	1	98,8±1,2	87,8±3,2	2,34±0,04	1806,1±60,4	0,52±0,02
	2	97,6±1,8	86,8±4,1	2,42±0,07	1796,4±58,4	0,54±0,04
	3	98,5±1,8	85,9±3,1	2,43±0,05	1788,0±60,1	0,54±0,02
Before the skin incision	1	87,5±1,1*Δ	62,4±2,6**□	1,9±0,06*Δ□	1495,5±70,6*Δ	0,19±0,01*Δ□
	2	91,4±1,2*Δ	72,6±1,9*Δ□	2,13±0,05*Δ	1612,1±64,4*	0,32±0,01*Δ□
	3	95,9±1,4	78,1±1,8*	2,28±0,09*	1703±58,4	0,41±0,01*
Traumatic stage	1	104,4±2,3***□	72,9±2,1***	2,12±0,09***	1769,9±82,3**	0,26±0,01***Δ□
	2	101,2±1,2**	75,8±2,2*	2,2±0,07*	1714,5±67,4	0,39±0,01***Δ□
	3	100,3±1,8	80,2±1,6	2,3±0,06	1713,2±60,9	0,47±0,02***□
End of the	1	98,1±2,1**	76,4±2,1*	2,21±0,05*Δ	1720,3±54,6	0,42±0,03***

operation	2	96,2±2,1**	76,9±2,0*	2,38±0,06Δ**	1615±58,1*	0,51±0,04**
	3	94,1±1,9**	78,6±2,4	2,45±0,08	1604±56,6*	0,59±0,03**

Note: * indicates statistically significant differences (p<0.05) compared to the initial preoperative values; ** indicates statistically significant differences (p<0.05) compared to the previous stage of the study; Δ indicates statistically significant differences (p<0.05) between the I and II groups; □ indicates statistically significant differences (p<0.05) compared to the III group.

Notably, vasopressor support was required for 100% of the patients in the 1st group, only 6 patients (42.8%) in the 2nd group, and only 2 women (11.7%) in the 3rd group.

Immediately before surgery, against the background of complete segmental sensory-motor and sympathetic blockade, a significant decrease in the index of tension (IOT) was recorded in patients in the 1st group, indicating a significant reduction in sympathetic influences. Moreover, the plasma cortisol concentration (CC) increased by 53.1%, which was due to the adequate protective effect of the hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal system on the restructuring of hemodynamics and the reduction in sympathetic influences.

At this stage, in the 2nd and 3rd groups of patients, the IOT tended to decrease by 298.2±20.2 units and 218.4±20.5 units, respectively. Moreover, the concentration of cortisol in the blood plasma significantly increased by 42% (2nd group) and 33.5% (3rd group). During the most traumatic stages of the operation, significant changes in the studied parameters of hemodynamics relative to those in the previous stage were not observed in any of the three groups. The most significant shifts continued to be observed in the 1st group of patients treated with spinal anaesthesia, while minimal hemodynamic disturbances were recorded in the 3rd group of patients treated with local anaesthesia (Table 2). Compared with those in the initial preoperative values and at the previous stage, the IOTs in all three groups were significantly greater (446.4±21.6 units, 450.2±23.4 units, and 490.8±24.3 units). The concentration of cortisol in the blood plasma also increased, reaching

743.3±38.4 nmol/L in the 1st group, 687.2±36.1 nmol/L in the 2nd group, and 677.6±37.4 nmol/L in the 3rd group. It should be noted that in none of the three groups did the studied parameters exceed the "stress norm", confirming the adequacy of anaesthesia.

The end of the operation in patients in all study groups was accompanied by a tendency to normalize the studied parameters of hemodynamics (Table 2); however, a hypodynamic mode of circulation continued to persist. In all patients, a significant decrease in heart rate (HR) and an increase in minute diuresis were recorded compared to those in the previous stage of the study. The cardiac indices (CIs) of patients in the 2nd and 3rd groups did not significantly differ from the preoperative values. Moreover, in patients in the 1st group, the MAP, CI, and minute diuresis rate remained significantly lower, at 76.4±1.6 mm Hg, 2.21±0.05 ml/min/m², and 0.42±0.03 ml/min, respectively (Table 2). The end of the operation was accompanied by moderate tension in the regulatory systems related to heart rate. The IOTs in patients in the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd groups significantly exceeded the preoperative absolute values by 23.6%, 17.4%, and 16.8%, respectively. The concentration of cortisol in the blood plasma at this stage of the study moderately decreased but did not significantly differ from that in the previous stage of the study (Table 3). The excretion of norepinephrine in the urine during the operation relative to the initial preoperative values increased by 13.1±1.1 nmol/L in the 1st group, 12.5±1.3 nmol/L in the 2nd group, and 12.3±1.3 nmol/L in the 3rd group.

Table 3

Some indicators of the autonomic, sympathoadrenal, and hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenocortical systems at the stages of anaesthesia and surgery in patients with moderately expressed MS (2.9-2 cm2)

The Studied Parameters	Groups	Stages of the research			
		On the operating table	Before the skin incision	Traumatic stage	End of the operation
Index of tension (IOT) units	1	336,4±20,6	229,4±208**Δ	446,4±21,6Δ	416,1±22,3*
	2	349,6±18,6	289,2±20,2**	450,2±23,4Δ	410,3±21,3*
	3	339,4±23,1	302,1±20,5	490,8±24,3*Δ	396,6±20,2*
Total cortisol (TC) nmol/L	1	410,8±26,4	628,2±26,1*□	734,3±38,4Δ	691,5±29,3□
	2	402,3±38,4	582,7±32,5*	687,2±36,1*Δ	627,4±30,6*
	3	390,5±34,3	521,4±30,8*	677,6±37,4*Δ	601,4±32,6*
NA, nmol/L (urine)	1	8,9±1,2	-	-	13,1±1,1*
	2	9,1±1,1	-	-	12,5±1,3*
	3	8,8±1,2	-	-	12,3±1,3*

Note: * indicates statistically significant differences (p<0.05) relative to the initial values; Δ indicates statistically significant differences (p<0.05) compared to the previous stage of the study; ** indicates statistically significant differences (p<0.05) between Groups I and II; □ indicates statistically significant differences (p<0.05) relative to Group III.

The above findings indicate moderately pronounced activation of the sympathoadrenal, hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal, and hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenocortical systems in response to surgical trauma, confirming the high effectiveness of the variants of central neuraxial block (CNB) used in this study.

Summarizing

1. Taken together, these findings suggest that for patients who undergo cesarean section (CS) and have moderately expressed mitral

stenosis and reduced coronary reserves at a gestational age of 34-36 weeks, the most reasonable method of anaesthetic management is balanced epidural anaesthesia with reduced concentrations of 0.375% bupivacaine in combination with fentanyl at a dose of 1.4 µg/kg and preventive analgesia with 100 ml of 1% paracetamol solution.

2. This method is highly effective, has minimal impact on central hemodynamics, and provides the opportunity for continuous postoperative pain management.

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